

Foraging decisions of a native whelk, *Nucella cingulata* and the effects of invasive mussel species on prey choice

Hannah Raven

Supervisor: Dr Mhairi Alexander

Co-Supervisor: Dr Tamara Robinson

16864484@sun.ac.za

Department of Conservation Ecology and Entomology

Centre for Invasion Biology

Private Bag XI

Matieland 7602

Abstract

Invasive species are considered one of the top threats to global biodiversity altering native habitat structure and functioning in a number of natural systems. The open coast along the west part of South Africa has been invaded by two mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Semimytilus algosus*. These species have altered the native species composition causing declines the native population of ribbed mussel *Aulacomya atra* and several other species. The alteration of mussel species composition on the shore has altered prey availability to native predators such as the dogwhelk *Nucella cingulata*. The overarching aims of this study were to determine the foraging behaviour of the native whelk and how a shift in species composition towards invasive mussel species has altered the whelks prey preference. Foraging behaviour was analysed to determine if prey selection by whelks was based on chemical cues (y-maze testing), tactile responses, (simultaneous prey presentation) or energy content gains (bomb calorimetry). Whelks did not show preference towards any particular mussel species when prey choice was made using chemical cues. This method of prey selection reflects the turbidity of wave exposed rocky-shore habitats where such cues would be unreliable. Prey selection during simultaneous presentations indicated a strong preference towards the two invasive mussel species with the invasive species being consumed more often than the native mussels. There was, however, no preference between both mussel species when presented simultaneously. Energy content did not vary between the three mussel species, therefore other variables must play a role during prey selection. The introduction of invasive mussel species has unmistakably altered native communities along South Africa's coastline not only in structure, but also in functioning with regards to species interactions. It is therefore important to keep in mind these interactions during decisions regarding management and removals of these mussel species for sound conservation of native biodiversity and the complex interactions that are maintained.

Introduction

Invasive species are a continuous threat to native biodiversity on a broad scale and can be considered a fundamental component to global change (Arim et al 2006). Invasive species have the ability to cause extensive environmental impacts, which include habitat degradation, complete removal of native species, alteration within ecosystem functioning, particularly within disturbance regimes (Mack and D'Antonio, 1998), and the further facilitation of new invasions (Mack et al 2000, Arim et al 2006). Anthropogenic activities including agriculture, aquaculture, recreation and transportation at a global level have further promoted the invasion process (Kolar and Lodge 2001). Several of these sectors have experienced immense economic impacts due to the costs associated with removal of alien invasive species that can alter the provisioning of ecosystem services (Keller et al 2008). It is therefore important to understand the effects of these invasions on ecosystem functioning and native diversity to manage these systems correctly to prevent devastating economic and ecological impacts (Cook et al 2007).

Marine ecosystems are considered highly susceptible to invasions and occur in a range of habitats including rocky shores, sandy sediments, marinas and harbours (Mead et al 2013). Most marine invaders are dispersed via various anthropogenic vectors including ballast water (Grosholz 2002), hull fouling (Bax et al 2003, Mead et al 2011), aquaculture (Griffith et al 2009) and the removal of natural barriers such as opening new channels between oceans (Rius and Shenkar 2012). Invasive species have caused havoc within the fishing industry often devaluing fisheries, fouling ships hulls and blocking intake pipes (Molnar et al 2008). Marine invasive species also have the ability to provide new habitat for native species, and potentially alter species richness (Crooks and Khim 1999, Grosholz 2002). These effects often come at the cost of loss in endemic biodiversity (Bax et al 2003). As a result invasive species have altered community structure and function, often outcompeting native biota with regards to resources including food and space along the rocky shores (Bax et al 2003, Molnar et al 2008, Jeschke et al 2014). Invasions are also known to affect species interactions including the predator prey dynamic that can potentially alter feeding patterns of native predators with the addition more profitable prey species (Rilov et al 2002).

South Africa's waters support an estimated 85 introduced and 39 cryptogenic marine species (Mead et al 2011). Although most of these invasions have been restricted to harbours which are sheltered from strong wave action (Robinson et al 2005, Griffiths et al 2009), there have been a number of invaders that have become established on open coast. One particular species has become so successful that it has been placed it on the top 100 most invasive species list, namely the Mediterranean mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (Lowe et al 2000, Branch and Steffini 2004, Branch et al 2008, Mead et al 2011). First observed in the late 1970s, *M. galloprovincialis* has now spread over 2000 km altering community composition and displacing local mussel species such as *Aulacomya atra* and *Choromytilus meridionalis* (Branch and Steffini 2004, Robinson et al 2007a, Robinson et al 2007b). A more recently introduced mussel *Semimytilus algosus* has also begun to dominate along parts of the same coast (de Greef et al 2013). This species was first detected in 2009 and, with the rapid expansion of its range, can now be found from Groenrivier to Misty cliffs (Figure 1) dominating the lower intertidal zone and decreasing the amount of space available for native mussel species (T. Robinson pers obs).

The community structure along the west coast has become dominated by invasive mussel species that have created a deeper mussel bed, increasing available habitat for infaunal species (Hammond and Griffiths 2005). The mussel beds provide shelter from strong wave action and are a food source for species such as whelks, polychaetes and arachnids (Branch and Steffini 2004, Hammond and Griffiths 2005). The predatory dogwhelk *Nucella cingulata* in particular is known to prey on the native mussel species *A. atra* as it was most dominant along the shore during the early invasion stages of *M.galloprovincialis* (Griffiths and Blaine 1994). The introduction of *M.galloprovincialis* and along with the recent arrival the arrival of *S. algosus* will likely affect existing predator-prey interactions as they have become an additional food resource (de Greef et al 2013). It is, therefore, important to understand the relationship between predator and prey to determine the potential effects the introduced species may have on these interactions. Predatory whelks have demonstrated complex behaviour towards prey size and species selection with the ability to learn (West 1986). In several cases whelks have also shown to display foraging decisions based on chemical cues released from their prey (Rilov 2002). Therefore the introduction of a new invasive species has the potential to once again alter foraging decisions of indigenous whelks while affecting trophic interactions (Nakaoka 2000).

Understanding the fundamental drivers behind interactions between invasive and native species is crucial towards the improvement of management and rehabilitation of invaded areas while allowing maintenance of native biodiversity (Molnar et al 2008). The west coast of southern Africa can be considered highly productive due to the upwelling system that provides nutrients to biodiversity rich waters (Branch and Griffiths 1988, Xavier et al 2007, Blanchette et al 2009). This biodiversity provides substantial ecosystem services to local and global communities such as food provision, minerals, tourism and sources of energy that play a crucial role in the international economy (Turpie et al 2003, Beaumont et al 2007). These ecosystem services are often taken for granted and regarded as common goods with no one taking responsibility when the consequences of environmental impact become reality (Hardin 1968, Ostrom et al 1999). As biodiversity is under constant threat of invasion of alien species, habitat alteration, pollution and climate change, it should be a priority to understand processes that threaten it (Ayyad 2003, Bax et al 2003, Molnar et al 2008).

The aim of this study was to investigate how the introduction of *M. galloprovincialis* and *S. algosus* impacts the predatory behaviour of *N. cingulata* and therefore to further understand the effects of invasive species on the native community. Specific aims questioned whether: 1) the native predatory whelks display chemical cue response to prey presentation, 2) the native predatory whelks display tactile cue responses to prey measured via simultaneous presentation, 3) the predatory whelk displays a preference to the invasive mussel species over the native, and 4) the prey preference can be related to the potential energy gains of the mussel species.

Material and Methods

Study site and sample collection

Samples were collected along the west coast of South Africa during February-April 2014. Native whelks (*Nucella cingulata*) were collected from Elands Bay (32°20'11.3"S, 18°18'52.1"E) and mussels were collected from Elands Bay (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Semimytilus algosus*), Bloubergstrand (33°48'20.1"S, 18°27'46.0"E; *M. galloprovincialis* and *Aulacomya atra*) and Hout Bay (34°02'55.3"S 18°21'38.9"E; *S. algosus*) (Figure 1). Whelks were sampled by scraping back mussel beds to reveal individuals sheltered within. Pilot studies suggested that there would be little response with younger individuals thus 200 whelks were selected based on size ranging between 19-32mm. The whelks were transported

Figure 1: Map of sites referred to in the text (de Greef et al, 2013)

in closed buckets (to prevent escape) filled with seawater collected on site. 350 mussels were removed from the intertidal mid shore with the use of a scraper, these were selected based on sizes ranging between 20-30mm for all species. Samples were then identified and placed in buckets with seawater from the collection site and returned to the laboratory at Stellenbosch University.

Maintenance whelks and mussels

Mussels and whelks were acclimated for approximately one week at $16^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ with 12 hour light: dark regimes. Whelks were placed in clear plastic tubs (five individuals per 13cm diameter tub) with each containing air-stones and sea water which was replaced daily. Mussels were separated by species and placed in plastic buckets (24cm), each containing air-stones with sea water that was changed every second day. All seawater used in the lab was be made artificially

(salinity 28-33ppt) and placed in a cooling system that maintains a constant water temperature to provide natural water conditions.

Prey –choice based on chemical cues

In order to determine whether whelks select prey based on the detection of chemical cues prey choice was tested by means of a y-maze set up. This would allow for the mixing of chemical signals within a limited environment for the whelk to detect and select prey. The y-maze was constructed using specially adapted PVC joints (Figure 2) that were secured at each end with a cap attached using marine silicone. Airstones were placed at the end of each arm to facilitate water movement. Y-mazes were soaked in seawater for 24 hours before use to prevent leaching of any chemicals from the marine silicone or PVC pipes that may have interfered with chemical cues produced by the mussels.

In order to determine whether there was adequate mixing of water allowing for chemical cues to be carried from the mussels to the whelk, the time taken for red dye to mix within the water of the y-maze was measured (32 seconds). Whelks were placed at the base of the y-maze and were presented with a choice between two mussel species that were placed at the end of each of the two Y-maze arms. Prey choice was compared between *M. galloprovincialis* vs. *A. atra*, *M. galloprovincialis* vs. *S. algosus* and *S. algosus* vs. *A. atra*, as well as choices between the same species at both end of the maze for a control. Control treatments were used to determine whether there was a side preference to a particular arm of the maze, other treatments were assigned randomly to avoid this bias. Fifteen replicates were performed for each combination set. The y-maze arena was left for 24 hours after which the choice was recorded if the whelk crossed over the threshold indicated in Figure 2. The maze was reset after each test by cleaning the maze and replacing water.

Figure 2: Y-maze set up with annotated dimensions (mm) for chemical cue prey choice experiment. Dotted lines indicate whelk starting position at the base and position of mussels in each arm.

Prey selection –based on simultaneous presentation

To tests for prey selection when whelks were allowed to access and consume mussels, simultaneous prey presentations were studied. Four whelks were randomly assigned a clear plastic tub (diameter 13cm) with 300ml seawater and one air stone with mussels presented in varying species combinations with a total 30 mussels per tub. Combinations included *A. atra* and *M. galloprovincialis* (15 mussels per species), *A. atra* and *S. algosus* (15 mussels per species), *M. galloprovincialis* and *S. algosus* (15 mussels per species), and all three species combined (10 mussels per species). Water was changed only every three days so as to limit disturbance and also to reduce biological waste build up within the tub. Mussel numbers were checked every three days and the empty shells of those consumed were removed and replaced. The experiment was run over a period of 20 days during which the number and species of mussels consumed was recorded for each setup combination. Control treatments included mussel combinations that were run for the same period of time as above without predatory whelks.

Energy content analysis

In order to determine whether prey selection was based on the potential energy gains provided by the mussel species, energy content was analysed. Mussel flesh was removed from 20 individuals per species with size ranging between 20-30mm in length. These samples were dried to a constant mass at 60°C and weight was recorded to 2 decimal places. Samples were then ground into powder form using a pestle and mortar and the energy value (kJ/g) of the flesh was determined by bomb calorimetry.

Statistical Analysis

Data recorded from the prey choice selection was analysed by performing a binomial analysis using the statistical package R (version 3.0.1) which stipulated the success of the whelk selecting one prey over another. Control treatments were randomly allocated.

In order to determine if there was a difference between the number of prey consumed during simultaneous prey presentation when comparing the three prey species, a repeated measures ANOVA was performed in the statistical package R (version 3.0.1). This analysis was chosen due to multiple dependent variables within the data. In order to quantify whether there were differences in energy content between the three mussel species a one-way ANOVA was performed using STATISTICA version 11 (StatSoft Inc., 2012).

Results

Prey choice based on chemical cues

A total of 15 trials were run per treatment with the y-maze with a success rate of 82%. During control treatments there was no trend towards either arm, thus excluding a bias towards a specific side of the y-maze. Prey selection experiments based on chemical cues (Table 1) indicated no preference towards selection of any prey species between any of the 6 treatments ($p > 0.05$). Although there was some trend towards the invasive species, there was no statistical confirmation that chemical cues played a role during prey selection.

Table 1: Binomial analysis comparing the probability of whelks selecting one prey over another in a y-maze set-up. A zero response was considered when no choice was made by the whelk in the allotted time period. Prey species are represented as follows: Mg- *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, Sa- *Semimytilus algosus*, and Aa- *Aulacomya atra*.

Prey 1	Prey 2	Successful trials	Zero responses	Prey 1 selected	Prey 2 selected	Probability of success	P value
Mg	Aa	14	1	9	5	0.64	0.42
Mg	Sa	13	2	8	5	0.62	0.58
Sa	Aa	11	4	3	8	0.73	0.23
Mg	Mg	12	3	7	5	0.58	0.77
Sa	Sa	12	3	9	3	0.75	0.15
Aa	Aa	12	3	5	7	0.42	0.77

Prey selection based on simultaneous presentation

In control trials there was >98% survival of mussels in the absence of predatory whelks, therefore mussel deaths were attributed to whelk predation which was also observed. The comparison between the native mussel *A. atra*, and the two invasive mussels *M. galloprovincialis* and *S. algosus* (Figure 3a) indicates a clear difference in the number of mussels consumed between the three mussel species ($F = 22.333$ $p = 0.006$). The comparison between the native mussel, *A. atra* and the more established invasive mussel species, *M. galloprovincialis* (Figure 3b) indicates significant difference between the number of mussels consumed of each mussel species ($F = 42.025$ $p = 0.023$) with the invasive mussel being consumed more often than the native. Comparing both invasive mussel species *M. galloprovincialis* and *S. algosus* (Figure 3c) there was no significance between the amount of each species consumed ($F = 3.218$ $p = 0.214$) with large error bars displaying the high variability of prey selection. The comparison between the native mussel species, *A. atra* and the recently established invasive mussel, *S. Algosus* displayed no difference in number of mussels consumed ($F = 11.25$ $p = 0.078$), however there is a strong trend towards consumption of the invasive mussel.

Figure 3: Mean (+/-SE) mussel consumption per treatment. A) Comparison between *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Aulacomya atra* and *Semimytilus algosus* (n=10 per species). B) Comparison between *M. galloprovincialis* and *A. atra* (n=15 per species). C) Comparison between *M. galloprovincialis* and *S. algosus* (n=15 per species). D) Comparison between *A. atra* and *S. algosus* (n=15 per species).

Energy content analysis

There was no significant difference in the energy content of the three mussel species ($F = 1.305$, $p = 0.297$, Figure 4).

Figure 4: Mean (+/- SE) available energy content (kJ/g) for *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Semimytilus algosus* and *Aulacomya atra*

Discussion

Invasive species are becoming an ever increasing threat to global diversity within all natural systems (Arim et al 2006) including the marine environment due to increased anthropogenic movement between areas (Grosholz 2002). South Africa's coastal waters have been severely affected by numerous invasions altering both species composition and structure (Mead et al 2011). The appearance of ecosystem engineers such as the invasive Mediterranean mussel, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and the bisexual mussel, *Semimytilus algosus* can impact native communities via habitat provisioning and altering fundamental species interactions (Branch and Steffini 2004, Robinson et al 2007a, Robinson et al 2007b). The introduction of these species has reduced the native mussel populations including the ribbed mussel, *Aulacomya atra* which commonly occurred along parts of the coastline (Wickens and Griffiths 1985). The modification of species composition along the shore is likely to affect interactions between the native community and the invasive species, particularly predator-prey interactions (Nakaoka 2000). The predatory dogwhelk *Nucella cingulata* is known to prey on the native ribbed mussel (Griffiths and Blaine 1994). However, the introduction of the invasive mussel species is likely to have affected existing predator-prey interactions due to the additional food resource (de Greef et al 2013). Therefore, understanding the fundamental drivers behind interactions between invasive and native species is crucial towards the improvement of management and rehabilitation of invaded areas while allowing maintenance of native biodiversity (Molnar et al 2008).

The chemosensory capabilities of most marine gastropods play a crucial role in foraging, reproduction and predator avoidance (Jacobsen and Stabell 2004, Ferner and Weissburg 2005, Chiu et al 2011, Durham et al 2012). However, the use of chemical cues within the water can often be reliant on the hydrological processing and can often cause odour filaments to dissolve due to increased turbulence (Ferner and Weissburg 2005). South Africa's coastline is well known for the strong wave action which plays an important role in shaping the community structure, particularly along the west coast (Branch and Griffiths 1988). Thus, it should not be surprising that *Nucella cingulata* exhibited no preference during prey selection based on chemical cues, as this would not be favoured due to high water movement and turbidity within their native habitat. It is, therefore, important to keep in mind that species interactions along the rocky shore are not

static and can be altered by environmental factors, in this case strong wave action (Gosnell et al 2012).

There were apparent differences between consumption of the three mussel species during simultaneous prey presentations. *N. cingulata* displayed substantial responses to simultaneous prey presentation, with strong preferences towards consumption of the invasive mussel species *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Semimytilus algosus*. When comparing the newly established mussel *S. algosus* and the native mussel *Aulacomya atra*, it should be noted that high variation between the number of mussels consumed may have weakened significance between number of prey consumed, and with increased sample size may change in outcome. This can be considered as a tactile response as whelks were able to crawl over prey and feel it before prey selection occurred. Tactile responses to simultaneous prey presentation should be considered more beneficial along South Africa's turbid coastline for the best allocation of energy (Chiu et al 2011).

Although the native whelks displayed strong preference to the invasive mussel species during simultaneous prey presentations, there was no indication that they would be rewarded with greater energy returns. The allocation of energy can be considered an important factor with regards to trade-offs between foraging time, consumption, predator avoidance and reproduction (Chiu et al 2011). Dogwhelks feed almost exclusively on mussels and barnacles utilising drilling and chemical dissolution techniques to consume prey (Rovero et al 1999). Although available energy content did not differ between the three mussel species, prey selection towards the invasive mussels may be based on other variables including shell thickness for easier drilling and less energy expenses.

Mussels have a substantial influence on overall community diversity, mediating environmental factors such as wave action, upwelling and deposition rate while acting as a central food source and regulating community structure (Robinson et al 2007a, Gosnell et al 2012). The introduction of invasive mussel species has caused a shift in species composition now dominating space that was previously inhabited by native fauna. (Robinson et al 2007a, Branch et al 2008). The alteration in available prey species for native predators evidently has transformed prey selection within the native community, particularly *N. cingulata* that historically preyed on the native ribbed mussel *A. atra* (Wickens and Griffiths 1985). Although this was not based on both

chemical cues and available energy content further work should look into other aspects of foraging behaviour including mussel thickness, location of drill holes and possibly logging behavioural data during feeding to determine reasons for prey selection and what implications the introduction of invasive species has on these interactions.

Implications for Conservation

The introduction of invasive mussel species has unmistakably altered native communities along South Africa's coastline not only in structure (Robinson et al 2007a), but also in functioning with regards to species interactions. This study has provided insight into foraging behaviours of a native predatory whelk species along the coast of South Africa, particularly focusing on predator prey interactions. It is evident that the arrival of the invasive mussels *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Semimytilus algosus* has altered prey selection of the native whelk species *Nucella cingulata* with a trend towards the invasive species and no difference between the two. This has provided essential information on how extensive the impacts of invasive mussels are on native communities. It is, therefore, important to keep in mind these interactions during decisions regarding management and removals of these mussel species for sound conservation of native biodiversity and the complex interactions that are maintained. Future work should focus on whether these patterns of prey selection hold true in the field where other environmental variables such as exposure may have an influence.

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